

Impact of Teacher- Pedagogical- Content- Knowledge on Achievement in Biology Concept among Secondary School Students in Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Ibrahim Abdulrahaman

Abdulrahaman.ibrahim@slu.edu.ng

[+2348034407082](tel:+2348034407082)

Department of Science Education, Sule Lamido University, kafin-Hausa, Jigawa State, Nigeria

Abstract

This paper investigated the Impact of Teacher- Pedagogical- Content- Knowledge on Achievement in Biology Concept among Secondary School Students in Jigawa State, Nigeria. An ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 3,045 students and 38 biology teachers spreads across the fifteen public science and technical senior secondary schools in Jigawa state while a sample of 443 students and 38 Biology teachers were selected as sample using systematic and census sampling technique respectively. Two measuring instruments were used for data collection namely; Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge Observation Schedule (TPCKOS) and Biology Achievement Test (BAT), the instruments were validated by six experts. The reliability of the instruments was found to be 0.91 for the Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge Observation Schedule and 0.77 for Biology Achievement Test. The data collected were analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviations to answer the research questions while ANOVA was used to test the research hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The results from the analysis revealed that there is significant difference in the academic achievement among senior secondary students based on their Biology Teachers level of pedagogical content knowledge. It concluded that the higher the teacher pedagogical content knowledge the higher will be the students academic achievement. The study recommended that State Ministry of Education, Science and Technology should organize regular workshops, seminars, conferences and lectures on teacher content knowledge and pedagogies for secondary school Biology teachers to improve their competence in applying method that will fit a particular topic in Biology for better students' academic achievement.

Keyword: Achievement, Teacher, Pedagogical, Content, knowledge, Biology.

Introduction

Biology as a branch of science and prerequisite subject for many fields of learning, contributes immensely to the technological growth of the nation. The study of Biology in Senior Secondary School can equip students with useful concepts, principles and theories that will enable them to face challenges (Abiodun & Victoria, 2023). The importance accorded Biology in the school curriculum from senior secondary school level to tertiary education reflects accurately the vital role played by biology in contemporary society. The importance of the subject is not restricted to the development of the individual alone, but for the advancement of the social, economic and political goals of countries all over the world. Furthermore, Biology provides a content in the training of students who want to study medicine, nursing, pharmacy, biochemistry, microbiology forestry, fisheries and so on. Requirement for a credit pass and above for senior secondary students in biology is necessary for admission into tertiary institution for science and science- related discipline (Duniya, 2016).

Despite the importance and applications of biology in many fields of learning, the performance of students in biology has been a source of concern to all stakeholders – the parents, teachers, students, science educators, researcher, government and general public. The performance of students in biology senior secondary school examinations has remained consistently poor. In recent times, the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) conducted by West African Examination Council (WAEC) revealed that a very few numbers of students performed better (WAEC, 2020). In Jigawa state which is the area of this study the story remained the same. Statistical evidence confirmed that, the percentage of students that passed Biology at credit level is consistently less than 40 % for the past 3 years between 2017 to 2019 (JERD, 2020). Several studies were conducted in and outside the shores of this country to investigate the causes of students' poor academic performance in science particularly Biology and the most recurring factor in all the reports were lack of teachers' content knowledge and pedagogical skills.

In support of the above reports, Usak et al, (2022) stated that one of the important factors affecting the quality of education is the quality of an individual teacher in the classroom. Teachers are vital for success or failure of an educational system; they implement the policies of an education system on the ground as well as designing, planning, and implementing a

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lesson. Educators are continuing to search for ways to improve student academic achievement and one way of doing so, is by enhancing the abilities of those who provide direct instruction to students. The relationship between teacher and student consists of numerous dynamics and interactions. Teachers must be prepared to address the diverse needs of their students. In the same vein, studies have shown that teachers’ expectations of their students can significantly affect their academic achievement (Yasin et al, 2022). However, the more qualitative and competent the teachers are, the more effective is the educational system.

Teacher qualities in education mainly focus on teacher content knowledge and pedagogical skills known as teacher pedagogical content knowledge (PCK). Pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) is the integration or amalgamation of pedagogy and content which covers the ‘what’ and ‘how’ of teaching. Teacher pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) is the knowledge that teachers develop over time, and through experience, about how to teach a particular content in particular ways to enhance students’ understanding (Shing, Saat and Loke, 2015). Teacher pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) was long searched by the scholars such as Tschannen and Hoy in the United States in their effort to elevate teaching to the professional status similar to that of doctor, lawyer and engineer. However, it is obvious that science curriculum consists of concepts, laws and theories which science teachers must be acquainted with to enable them transform valid knowledge of science effectively to their students. Their ability to impart scientific knowledge to learners must go beyond verbalization of the basic terms of science. No matter how brilliant a teacher may be, the moment he or she could not interpret the subject-matter knowledge to facilitate student learning, he or she has not achieved anything (Eporyi & Arko, 2021). Moreover, in recent years, issues on teachers’ content knowledge and pedagogy skills have attracted increasing attention from several agents of change in educational industry. In recent time, Kaduna state government conducted a competency test for their teachers. The results from the test indicated that over twenty-one thousand teachers failed the test, as a results of this such teachers were sacked (Aina, 2020). Researchers such as Josiah & Oluwatogin (2017) and Ishola & Udofi (2017) agreed that teachers are the most important school-based determinant and students’ performance is more heavily influenced by the teacher’s quality in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy skills than by students’ prior academic record or school a student attends. As such this paper set to find out whether teacher content knowledge and pedagogical skills has any impact on students’ academic achievement.

Biology is a compulsory subject for both art and science students in Nigerian senior secondary schools. Therefore, requirement for a credit pass and above in Biology is necessary for universities admission into science and science- related disciplines. However, despite the importance of Biology, the results from record analysis of West African Examination Council disclosed that students’ academic performance in Biology has been poor and this posed serious challenge to educational stakeholders (Fareo, 2019). In line with the above assertion, statistical evidence revealed that the percentage of students in Jigawa state that passed Biology at credit level is consistently less than 40 % for the past 3 years between 2017 to 2019 (Jigawa State Education Resource Department, 2020). Consequently, this poor performance lead government of Jigawa State to suspend West African Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) for good two years across the government owned senior secondary schools (MOESATJS, 2020).

Table 1 Statistics of Jigawa State Biology Results for May/June WASSCE

Year	No. of Candidates Reg.	Credit Scores	Percentage %
2017	9,769	3,346	34.25
2018	12,869	3,986	30.95
2019	13,039	5,144	39.45

Source: Jigawa State Education Resource Department (JERD), 2020

In the same vein, the growing rate of students’ failures in Join Admission and Matriculation Board Examination (JAMB) which is the other side of coin and prerequisite for admission into Universities, Colleges of Education and other institution in Nigeria deprived many students’ admission. In support of the above statement Oloyede (2021) confirmed that the performance of students in Join Admission and Matriculation Board Examination (JAMB) is poorer than what was recorded within the past three years. These reasons have injected worry into the minds of all those who have concern for Nigerian youths. However, in a state or country where a greater number of youths are deprived for Education due to Examination failure or dropouts, social vices such as armed robbery, raping, bandit, kidnapping and others will be on the increase.

Ahmad, Sultana and Jamil (2023) stated that teachers and the quality of teaching are often considered the most critical elements of students’ success in learning Biology. Effective teaching in the classroom can help students to develop positive attitude towards learning. In the same vein, attitude of a student to a particular subject matter could go a long way to determine the student’s academic achievement in that subject. Globally, the pre- requisite of teaching profession has focused more on content knowledge and pedagogical skills as requirement for successful teaching, which this study is concerned about specifically teachers of Biology (Tari & Ibrahim, 2020). In spite of this, statistical evidence revealed that, many teachers of

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Biology in Jigawa State are graduates of microbiology, biochemistry, plant science and Agricultural science among others, who did not receive adequate training and knowledge of many concepts in Biology in respect of pedagogical skills. It was clear that, it is possible for out-of-field teaching to compromise teaching competence and disrupt teacher's identity, self-efficacy, and well-being. However, does teachers qualities (content knowledge and pedagogical skills) have any impact on students' achievement? As such, this study is set to find out the impacts of teacher pedagogical content knowledge on Biology students' academic achievement among Senior Secondary School in Jigawa state.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this paper are to:

1. Determine the level of Biology teacher pedagogical content knowledge among Senior Secondary Schools in Jigawa State.
2. To ascertain the impact of Biology teachers' pedagogical content knowledge on the academic achievement of Senior Secondary Students' studying Biology in Jigawa State.

Research Questions

Based on the objectives of the paper, the following research questions were poised:

1. What are the levels of pedagogical content knowledge among Senior Secondary School Biology Teachers in Jigawa State?
2. What is the difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary students based on level of Biology Teachers pedagogical content knowledge?

Hypotheses

This hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of students based on level of Biology teachers pedagogical content knowledge.

Methodology

Ex- post-facto research design was used for the purpose of this research to gather the data needed. The population of the study consist of all Science and Technical Senior Secondary School II students in Jigawa state and their corresponding Biology teachers, with a total population of three thousand and forty-five students and thirty-eight Biology teachers. The sample size of the study were 443 biology students and 38 biology teachers. Two instruments were used for the purpose of data collection namely; Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge Observation Schedule (TPCKOS) and Biology Achievement Test (BAT). TPCKOS was developed by the researcher using teacher evaluation form and undergraduate teaching practice assessment form while BAT was developed by the researcher using West African Examination Council (WAEC) past questions paper between 2018-2022. The two instruments were validated by six experts in the area of science education biology, educational psychology, and test and measurement. The reliability of instruments was found to be 0.91 for the Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge Observation Schedule (TPCKOS) and 0.77 for Biology Achievement Test (BAT) using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC). Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge Observation Schedule (TPCKOS) was administrated to the sampled biology teacher while Biology Achievement Test was administrated to the sampled students. The scripts were collected and marked for each teacher and their corresponding students. Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge Observation Schedule (TPCKOS) was used to identify the level of teachers' PCK which classified into three groups; High teacher PCK, moderate teacher PCK, and low teacher PCK. The achievement scores of students under the three categories of teachers were later compared to find out the difference. The data collected for the study were analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while ANOVA to test the stated null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the levels of pedagogical content knowledge among senior secondary school biology teachers in Jigawa State?

Table 2: Levels of Biology Teacher PCK

Level of teachers' PCK	Number	Percentage %
High PCK	13	34.2 %
Moderate PCK	11	29.0%
Low PCK	14	36.8 %
Total	38	100 %

Table 2 showed that, 34.2 % of the biology teachers have high Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge of teaching biology, then 29.0 % have moderate Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge while 36.8% have low teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge. The results revealed higher number of biology teachers with low level of Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge with 36.8%.

Research Question 2: What is the difference in the academic achievement scores of senior secondary students based on their Biology Teachers level of pedagogical content knowledge?

To answer this research question Means and Standard deviations are required. The achievement test means scores of students taught Biology by Teachers pedagogical content knowledge were subjected to descriptive statistics. Mean and standard deviation were computed and used to draw Table 3 below:

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Achievement Based on their Teachers' Levels of PCK

	N	Mean	Std. D
High teacher PCK	230	60.96	16.49
Moderate teacher PCK	123	46.70	14.44
Low teacher PCK	90	41.66	13.45

The result in Table 3 shows that, the mean academic achievement scores of students with teacher of high PCK is 60.96 followed by students with teacher of moderate PCK 46.70 and then students with teacher of low PCK 41.66. The results revealed a mean difference in favor of students with teachers of high pedagogical content knowledge. Hence, difference existed between Senior Secondary Biology students' academic achievement based on their teachers with high, moderate and low pedagogical content knowledge.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of students based on their Biology Teachers pedagogical content knowledge.

To test this hypothesis, the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Biology base on Teachers pedagogical content knowledge were subjected to ANOVA test statistic and summary of analysis as shown on Table 4 below:

Table 4: ANOVA Table for Student Achievement based on their Teachers' PCK

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	31019.55	2	15509.778	66.343	0.001
Within Groups	102863.185	440	233.780		
Total	133882.740	442			

Table 4 results show F -test between the achievements mean scores of students based on Biology Teachers pedagogical content knowledge. The result shows that p- value of 0.001 is less than 0.05 level of significance, which indicated significant difference. Therefore, the difference between senior secondary students' academic achievement based on Biology Teachers pedagogical content knowledge is significant. Hence, the stated null hypothesis is thereby rejected. This means, there is significant difference in the academic achievement of students based on Biology Teachers pedagogical content knowledge. To

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find out where the difference lies, the groups were subjected to multiple comparisons statistic and summary of analysis as shown on table 5 below:

Table 5: Post Hoc of Students' Achievement based on their teachers PCK

(I) Teacher PCK	(J) Teacher PCK	Mean difference (I-J)	Sig
High teacher PCK	Moderate PCK	14.25790*	0.001
	Low PCK	19.29855*	0.001
Moderate teacher PCK	High PCK	- 14.25790*	0.001
	Low PCK	5.04065*	0.018
Low teacher PCK	High PCK	-19.29855*	0.001
	Moderate PCK	-5.04065*	0.018

Table 5 is a Post hoc calculation identified exactly where the differences lie. After ANOVA showed significant difference in the students' academic achievement based on Biology Teachers pedagogical content knowledge group. Therefore, post hoc revealed that, the difference lies between high and low teacher pedagogical content knowledge group with mean difference of 19.29855.

Discussion of Findings

The study sought to find out the Impact of Teacher Pedagogical Content Knowledge on Achievement in Biology Concept among Secondary School Students in Jigawa State. Two research questions were asked and one null hypothesis was tested. The results of data analysis of the research questions and null hypothesis are hereby discussed.

The results of analysis presented in table 2 show higher level of biology teachers with low pedagogical content knowledge 36.8% which is higher than moderate and high teacher pedagogical content knowledge categories. This finding is in agreement with that of Eporyi and Arko (2022) who investigate levels of Biology teacher pedagogical content knowledge. The result of their study indicated high level of low teacher pedagogical content knowledge among inexperienced biology teachers. In contrary Ahmad, Sultana and Jamil (2023) result indicates a higher moderate level of teacher pedagogical content knowledge in biology. In the same vein, Usak, Uygun and Duran (2022) finding also indicated higher of moderate level of teacher pedagogical content knowledge in biology.

The analysis in Table 3 and 4 indicates significant difference in the academic achievement of students based on their Biology teachers with low, moderate and high pedagogical content knowledge. This means, the higher the teacher pedagogical content knowledge the higher will be the students' academic achievement and vice versa. This finding is in agreement with that of Usak, Uygun & Duran (2022) whose findings revealed a significant difference in the academic achievement of students based on their Biology teachers with low, moderate and high pedagogical content knowledge. The result of Kuluca (2021) also support the finding of this study that, teacher is teaching experience is a major source of teacher pedagogical content knowledge and there is statistically significant difference between teacher teaching experience and student academic achievement. In the same line Aporyi and Arko (2021) find out that students that are taught by teacher with high and moderate pedagogical content knowledge performed better than those taught by teacher with low pedagogical content knowledge. This result also corroborates the findings of Festus (2022) which shows that if students are taught by teachers of high content knowledge they perform better and this has shown even in the students' academic performance. Collaborating this assertion are Olfos, Goldrine and Estrella (2014) whose found a strong impact between teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and students' understanding in learning.

However, on the contrary findings, Odumosu, Olisama and Fisayo (2018) revealed that there is no significant impact of teachers' pedagogical content knowledge on students' academic achievement in Algebra. Anita (2023) also reported in her Findings that teacher's qualification does not influence students' academic achievement. Usak, Uygun & Duran (2022) also found no statistical significance difference between teacher pedagogical content knowledge and teaching experience on difference categories of teacher on student academic achievement in science subject.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that there was a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology based on the level of Teachers pedagogical content knowledge, this means the higher the teacher pedagogical content knowledge the higher will be the students academic achievement.

Recommendations

Based on the forgone submission, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) The State Ministry of Education, Science and Technology should organize regular workshops, seminars, conferences and lectures on teacher content knowledge and pedagogies for secondary school Biology teachers to improve their competence in applying methods that will fit a particular topic in Biology for better students' academic achievement. Once teachers know what to do, how to do it, and feel good about doing it, chances of students' success are enhanced greatly.
- 2) The nature of Biology content is such a way that it contains concepts, sub- concepts and linkage between the concepts, Biology teachers should use teaching methodologies that ensure students positive attitude toward the subject at Senior Secondary Schools.

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